

largement of the mediastinal glands, and, combined with the ingestion of bismuth, it shows the position of strictures, the size and location of diverticula, and the size of the dilated esophagus.

The technic of esophagoscopy under local and under general anesthesia is described in detail.

2. Causes, Symptoms, Pathology, Diagnosis and Treatment. DR. CHEVALIER JACKSON, Pittsburgh.

Stenoses of the esophagus may be classified as inflammatory, neoplastic, compressive, spastic and angio-neurotic.

The inflammatory stenoses may be edematous or cicatricial; the neoplastic, benign or malignant. The compressive may be due to malignant, benign or inflammatory, or peri-esophageal lesions, or to aneurysm or enlargement of the left auricle. Compression stenosis is also frequently caused by a pulsion diverticulum of the esophagus itself when the pouch is full of blood. Spastic stenoses are usually seen at the cricoid level, due to spasmodic contraction of the inferior constrictors, especially the orbicular fiber, along with the adjacent orbicular fiber of the esophageal wall. The next most frequent spastic stenosis is at the hiatus, the contraction being due to the traction of the diaphragmatic musculature and the small bundles of fibers given off from the diaphragm and attached to the esophagus. Angio-neurotic edema producing severe stenosis of the esophagus has been observed by Arrowsmith.

The etiology varies with the character of the stenosis. Inflammatory stenoses are most frequently caused by swallowing corrosives, but they may be due to stasis of food halted by spasmodic stenosis. Other causes are the traumata of foreign bodies, the mixed infections associated with lues and with tuberculosis of the esophageal wall.

The cause of neoplastic stenoses, like that of neoplasms elsewhere, is unknown. Inflammatory processes and their end-results probably contribute to the etiology by affording a favorable soil.

Spastic stenoses may be local or general. Local stenosis is often the result of a "vicious circle" started by rapid eating, with its associated gulping of large boluses of poorly masticated food, followed by stasis of the food, inflammation and erosion, which, in turn, serve as a source of reflex excitement of more frequent and prolonged spasm, this inflammatory process being thus increased. The general causes of spastic stenosis are dependent upon some basic nerve-disorder, probably more functional than organic.

Pulsion diverticulum, as demonstrated by Killian, is chiefly caused by insufficient support of the esophageal wall between the fundiform and oblique fiber of the inferior constrictor.

Extensive consideration of the symptomatology is useless, inasmuch as any abnormal sensation whatever, referable to the esophagus, is an indication for esophagoscopy, by which, rather than by symptoms, the diagnosis is to be made. An otherwise altogether unaccountable cough, "globus hystericus," and the filling to overflowing of the pyriform sinuses with secretions, are some of the signs which may lead to the diagnosis of esophageal stenosis.

Radiography is of the greatest usefulness in demonstrating the size and extent of dilatation and diverticula, as well as assisting in making the diagnosis of their presence. Fluoroscopy affords very important aid by determining the functional activity of the esophagus during the act of swallowing. Taken alone, however, these means may lead to error.

The bougie, passed blindly, is of no use for diagnostic purposes. The differential diagnosis of lues, tuberculosis, and malignancy is made by exclusion and by biopsy. The other types of stenosis are diagnosed by characteristic signs, which are detailed by the author.

Treatment should never be instituted while the patient is in the condition of water starvation. Enteroclysis or hypodermoclysis should be begun immediately. Immediate gastrostomy by the general surgeon, preferably under local anesthesia, should be performed when the patient has had little or no water for as much as four days.

Edematous inflammatory stenoses are best treated by having the patient swallow small doses of bismuth with a little calomel, both given dry on the tongue.

Cicatrical stenoses, in the author's experience, are best treated by filiform silk-woven bougies passed esophageally.

Benign and endo-esophageal growths are probably readily removable, though they are so rare that accurate data are lacking.

Malignant stenoses of the esophagus are regarded by general surgeons as inoperable. There is reason to hope, however, that, when early diagnosis is possible, transthoracic esophageal resection may be a justifiable procedure.

Spasmodic stenoses are best treated by divulsion. For this the author prefers a mechanical divulsor, such as that of Mosher, passed by sight through the esophagoscope.

The treatment of compressive stenoses obviously depends upon the nature of the compressive mass.

Pulsion diverticula, according to the consensus of opinion, steadily increase in size and severity of symptoms; consequently amputation of the sac by the surgeon, operating through the neck, is indicated. The operation with the esophagoscopic aid, devised by Dr. Otto C. Gaub, has been successfully employed by the author in two cases. This method is described and illustrated with three figures.

DISCUSSION.

DR. ROSS HALL SKILLERN recommended the "Schwebe" laryngoscope, which, with the suspension apparatus, gives a technic as simple as the passing of a naso-pharyngoscope into the nose. With the tongue-depressor and the apparatus for lifting up the larynx the pyriform sinuses and the upper part of the larynx could be shown completely, without lifting the cricoid cartilage entirely. The instrument was fitted with a double light. The tube was passed, as one would pass the naso-pharyngoscope, and slipped down below the cricoid cartilage. By comparing this with the other method, he had found it the simpler. He could see directly into the larynx. Children, as a rule, stood the esophagoscope badly, but under the "Schwebe" or suspension apparatus they would stand it for hours, or as long as necessary. He had had no child, thus far, to "go bad" with the "Schwebe" in position.

DR. SIDNEY YANKAUER recounted an experience with a stricture at the cardiac end of the stomach. The patient had suffered for many years from cardio-spasm, and many attempts had been made to dilate the cardia, all without the slightest effect upon the cardio-spasm. The man was unable to swallow other than liquid food, most of which came back into the mouth. He finally came into the hands of Dr. Willy Meyer, who, in the differential pressure chamber, opened the thorax, found the dilated portion of the esophagus, which he corrected by plicating, but without improvement. The patient was put in the chamber again and an operation similar to Mikulicz's pyloroplasty performed on the cardia through the chest wall. There resulted not the slightest improvement in the swallowing or in the cardio-spasm. Dr. Meyer then turned the patient over to him to see what could be accomplished with the esophagoscope. Upon putting in the instrument, the scar-tissue from the plications could be seen, forming ridges at the antero-lateral portion of the cardia; beyond this, a bend of the lumen was located at the cardia, which it was impossible to pass. The lumen of the cardia was merely a slit. Attempts to pass through this brought so much pressure to bear upon the sides of the esophagus that it was impossible to proceed. To pass and straighten out this tissue was a problem. He made for the purpose a wire probe which consisted of small joints, about a quarter of an inch long, so constructed that it would bend in one direction but could not return beyond a straight line. His idea was to use the curved part to go around the ridge to rotate the instrument and then to pass the straight part into the stomach. After several attempts he finally succeeded in straightening out the ridge and in passing a narrow tube beyond the ridge. He then saw what seemed to be a string coming out from the lumen of the cardia. It proved to be a silk suture from the cardio-plastic operation. Subsequently he found another stitch which he cut and removed. Following the removal of these two stitches the scar tissue softened up considerably, after which the gastroscope could be passed. After this the patient could swallow liquid food without difficulty, and some semi-solid food. He then passed the gastroscope and manipulated the head and shoulders in an effort to loosen up the cicatricial tissue. The patient's condition improved to such an extent that he could swallow gruels and semi-solid foods, but not solid food.

The case illustrated what can be accomplished by the exercise of patience and a certain amount of resourefulness.

DR. SAMUEL IGLAUER described a procedure employed in the treatment of a case of complete obstruction of the esophagus following typhoid fever, occurring in a boy about 10 years of age. A gastrostomy had been performed, through which the patient had been fed for a number of years. In order to measure the thickness of the obstruction, an olive-tipped bougie was passed from the stomach into the esophagus and another was passed through the mouth and the distance between the two olives was determined by an x-ray picture. The olives were found to be slightly overlapped and about one-sixteenth of an inch apart.

Esophagoscopy both from the oral and the stomach-end of the esophagus failed to reveal any fistulous tract through the obstruction. A few days later, working in conjunction with Dr. Murphy, of Cincinnati, an at-

tempt was made to relieve the obstruction by an original method. An esophagoscope was introduced through the stomach-end of the esophagus and at the same time a second esophagoscope was introduced through the oral end. Both tubes were introduced as far as the obstruction, there being an observer for each instrument. When the light in one instrument was turned out the glow of the light in the other could at times be seen transilluminating the obstruction.

With an electro-cautery an attempt was then made to burn through the transilluminated diaphragm from above. The cautery was followed by a slender bougie which apparently passed through, but digital examination showed the bougie under the mucous membrane in the stomach. The bougie had evidently dissected up the mucosa of the esophagus and passed down into the stomach wall. After a few days the patient was removed from the hospital, contrary to advice. While on the train on his way home he began to swallow naturally and this continued up to the time of his death, which occurred about three weeks after the operation. Evidently the lumen of the esophagus had been restored and if the procedure outlined above were followed more cautiously it would prove more successful.

DR. GEORGE F. COTT added a third condition to the two mentioned by Dr. Mosher in which the esophagoscope could not or should not be passed. He cited a case in which the patient could not swallow, and in whom, under ether, the esophagoscope could not be passed after strenuous efforts for some time. Upon further investigation it was discovered that there was ankylosis of the cervical vertebrae from syphilis.

DR. G. HUDSON-MAKUEEN asked if Coley's fluid (mixed toxins of bacillus prodigiosus and streptococcus erysipelatosus) had been tried in malignant disease of the esophagus. Many cases of marvelous cures have been reported, not only by Coley himself, but by other distinguished surgeons in this country and abroad, and it would seem that, unless there were some contra-indication against its use, it might prove to be quite as efficient, if not more so, than any of the other methods which have been suggested, not excluding radium. He had had the pleasure recently of talking with Dr. Coley about the preparation of the "fluid," and about its use—a work in which he has been engaged for more than twenty years—and he was encouraged to hope that it might be useful in the class of cases under discussion. He would be glad to hear the opinion of the essayists on the subject.

DR. ROBERT LEVY said that the sign of which Dr. Jackson had spoken—the accumulation of secretion in the pyriform sinus—had been observed by him in cases of tuberculosis with painful deglutition. He had seen cases in which these sinuses were completely filled.

DR. R. H. CRAIG suggested the use of the high frequency fulguration-spark in the treatment of inoperable cases of this nature. He cited a case in which the pain absolutely disappeared and the growth was greatly reduced. The patient, however, died six months later. In another case of malignant disease involving the sphenoid and the naso-pharynx, after a month's treatment this disappeared and the growth was much reduced in size. He believes the high frequency fulguration-spark is of great value

in alleviating pain and diminishing the growth in these desperate cases. Where the growth is accessible carbon dioxide snow may be useful.

DR. JOSEPH C. BECK asked Dr. Jackson if he had employed the Abderhalden test for carcinoma. He also asked Dr. Jackson to specify, in closing the discussion, what he meant by "small quantities" of radium. He had employed nineteen milligrams of the salt or ten milligrams of the pure radium element.

DR. MOSHER, in closing the discussion, said Dr. Skillern's remarks interested him. He had tried the procedure of suspension esophagoscopy and had found it satisfactory in the examination of the upper part of the esophagus. He had not had the trouble with the breathing which Dr. Skillern mentioned; in fact, he had been astonished to see how little trouble he had had in this regard. Referring to Dr. Iglauer's case, he said he had reported a case three or four years ago where the same procedure was used. It was a case of absolute stenosis of the esophagus, and he attacked it from above and below. The procedure which helped was that of picking the stricture apart, ballooning, and picking it apart again. In his experience, perforating the esophagus led to fatal mediastinitis.

DR. JACKSON, in closing the discussion, said Dr. Mosher was the highest authority on the anatomy of the esophagus. Dr. Jackson believed that all the early esophagoscopists and many of to-day mistook the hiatal constriction for the cardia. The question of anesthesia was a matter of personal equation. Every man should select the instruments which suit his needs best, and so it is with anesthesia. The method should be selected which suits the operator's needs in the particular case. Personally the speaker had been very much interested in the case reported by Dr. Yankauer. He thought the work of Dr. Yankauer and Dr. Meyer would open a new field. The procedure mentioned by Dr. Iglauer was exceedingly interesting, and while it was a failure in the case cited, it was justifiable in absolutely impervious strictures, and offered hope of success. In cooperating with Dr. Brenneman he had passed a tube to serve as a staff upon which Dr. Brenneman cut the occluding cicatrix from below the externally opened stomach. Such procedures were, of course, indicated only in impermeable occlusion. If any lumen existed, however small, it could be cured by the safer endoscopic methods. Dr. Cott's point was well taken.

Answering Dr. Goldstein's question concerning recurrence of spasmodic stenosis the speaker cited a case of spasmodic stenosis, in which he absolutely failed. He stretched the abdominal esophagus so completely that he could see into the stomach, and yet recurrence took place. This was, however, his only failure so far. The patient became discouraged and finally gave up treatment.

Referring to Dr. Makuen's remarks concerning Coley's fluid, he said the method was applicable to sarcoma, and that it was in this disease that radium also gave best results, carcinoma being less amenable. Both methods could be used in the same patient. He suggested that in the cases of filling of the pyriform sinuses by secretions, mentioned by Dr. Levy, there might possibly be spasm in the crico-pharyngeal muscle causing temporary stenosis with resultant filling of the pyriform sinuses, or, in other instances, a disinclination to swallow because of the odynophagia

which might exist. Or, in still other instances, an actual organic esophageal stenosis due to tuberculous infiltration of the "party wall" might be present. Nevertheless, Dr. Levy's point was well taken. Dr. Jackson hoped that fulguration and carbon dioxid snow would be thoroughly tried out, but he had had no experience with either. He had not employed the Abderhalden test, as suggested by Dr. Beck, but all diagnostic methods should be used. With reference to the dosage of radium, he said a small dose, such as ten milligrams, acts as an irritant, because it cannot be left long enough in the esophagus. A hundred milligrams left in for an hour or more was usually required. He did not speak as an authority; he depended upon Dr. W. H. Cameron and Dr. William Proescher for dosage and duration of the radium application in each particular case.

Suspension Laryngoscope in Children. DR. ROBERT LEVY, Denver.

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DISCUSSION.

DR. SIDNEY YANKAUER agreed with all Dr. Levy said concerning suspension laryngoscopy. He has performed a number of operations with this apparatus, one of which he reported before the Eastern Section of this Society. After several operations by the general surgeons, the patient's neck was so scarred that the lumen of the larynx was so small that he could hardly get a probe through. The arytenoids were so adherent to the epiglottis that by the ordinary direct methods the lumen could not be seen, but with suspension laryngoscopy this could be accomplished. The passage of the first probe was followed by a larger, and finally he could pass a uterine dilator. By means of the uterine dilator he could stretch the larynx sufficiently to get a rubber tube in, which was left *in situ* for two weeks, when a larger one was used. It was thus possible, finally, to introduce the intubation tube. The boy is now going about, and has been wearing the intubation tube for about four months. The suspension laryngoscope had been modified by Killian himself as well as by others. The new model which Killian has brought out does not appear as useful as the original model. He has not been able to bring the anterior commissure into view with the new device.

DR. SAMUEL IGLAUER was interested in Dr. Levy's remarks, and agreed with practically every point. While it is true that the procedure is less difficult in children, it can be carried out satisfactorily in adults. In bringing the anterior commissure into view, one should use counter-pressure with Albrecht's instrument, or the finger. Killian recommends a dose of codein preliminary to the anesthetic, in children. He has frequently followed this suggestion. Atropin should be used with ether in order to dry up the secretions.

He has tried tonsil removal under suspension, but thinks the Beck method far superior and much simpler than that of Killian. Referring to the removal of a broken safety-pin from the larynx of the child, 5 years of age, he really did not completely suspend the patient. He introduced the spatula and while supporting the spatula (and thus the patient's head) with his left hand, he could see the foreign body and remove it immediately with the forceps in his right hand. He has recently intro-